

Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation of a Morphing Wing Section with a Metamaterial-Based Trailing Edge

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multidisciplinary design optimisation (MDO) of a morphing wing section using a metamaterial-based trailing edge. The study investigates whether a metamaterial lattice structure can effectively replace a conventional hinged control surface and evaluates the trade-offs between aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and control authority. A monolithic MDO framework integrates aerodynamic, structural, and control analyses in a coupled loop, using a genetic algorithm to optimise the lattice geometry and actuators configuration. The objective function maximises range and endurance of a fixed-wing UAV, considering both flight performance in cruise and loiter and actuators' mass penalty. The results show that the proposed design achieves the required trailing-edge deflections with minimal control force and reduced mechanical complexity. Limitations due to modelling simplifications are discussed, and directions for future work are outlined.

Nomenclature

AR	Wing aspect ratio
c_D	Drag coefficient
$c_{D_{aft}}$	Airfoil drag coefficient
C_{Di}	Induced drag coefficient
c_L	Lift coefficient
c_M	Pitch moment coefficient
c_p	Pressure coefficient
\mathbf{d}	Vector of design variables
d_{Latt}	Metamaterial lattice thickness
d_{rib}	Rib spacing
e	Oswald's efficiency factor
E_{batt}	Battery energy
E_{loiter}	Endurance during the loiter
E_{norm}	Normalized endurance
F	Actuation force

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g	Gravitational acceleration
g_k	Inequality constraint function
h_k	Equality constraint function
m_{act}	Actuator mass
m_{batt}	Battery mass
$m_{batt,0}$	Default battery mass
m_{tow}	Aircraft take-off weight
<i>MDO</i>	Multidisciplinary design optimisation
N_g	Total number of inequality constraints
N_h	Total number of equality constraints
n_{rib}	Number of ribs
p	Penalty parameter
R_{cruise}	Range at the cruise regime
R_{norm}	Normalized range
S_w	Wing surface area
<i>TE</i>	Trailing edge
TE_{rot}	Angular deflection of the trailing edge
α	Angle of attack
η_{total}	Total efficiency factor
ρ_0	Air density at sea level
Φ	Unit cell angle

1. Introduction

Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation (MDO) provides a powerful tool for the design of complex systems such as morphing wings, which aim to improve aerodynamic performance across different flight regimes compared to traditional fixed wings. At the same time, morphing wings can benefit from advanced materials and control strategies, potentially reducing wing weight and/or wing loading. This work aims to explore the possibility of replacing a conventional UAV wing and aileron by a morphing trailing edge incorporating a metamaterial lattice hinge.

The motivation for this research comes from the limited application of metamaterials in morphing wing designs. Some previous studies have led to compliant rib mechanisms using superelastic materials [1], [2]. Recent research has resulted in a unit cell design with optimised tension–twist thickness [3]. Another proposed solution for a hingeless trailing edge involves a fishbone structure [4]. While many different and complex approaches have been explored, the straightforward replacement of a hinge with a metamaterial lattice, as proposed the "Blinded text" project [5], has not yet been investigated. An MDO architecture for a morphing wing using a metamaterial lattice was introduced in "Blinded reference"; however, this work provides an MDO solution only for the trailing edge.

Based on the reasons outlined above, this paper addresses the following two research questions. The first is: Can a metamaterial lattice effectively replace the conventional trailing-edge hinge in a morphing wing section? This question is examined from structural, aerodynamic, and control perspectives. The second question is: What are the trade-offs between aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and control authority in such a morphing configuration? This

is investigated through the MDO of a morphing wing section incorporating a metamaterial-based trailing edge. The results of this analysis represent the main contribution of the paper.

This paper is structured into six sections. The Introduction and Literature Review sections establish the motivation for the study, provide background information, and summarise recent developments in the relevant research domains. Section Three presents the design of a morphing wing section incorporating a metamaterial lattice, along with a detailed description of the methodologies employed. Section Four reports the results obtained from the multidisciplinary design optimisation process. These findings are further analysed and discussed in section Five. Finally, section Six concludes the paper by summarising its key contributions and outlining potential directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

This section introduces recent advancements in the fields of morphing wings, metamaterials, and multidisciplinary design optimisation.

2.1. Morphing Wing Technologies

Morphing wing technology is as old as powered flight itself—the Wright brothers used wing twisting to control roll in 1903. However, recent advancements in material technologies have opened new possibilities for morphing applications. Technologically, it is now feasible to morph any part of the wing. [6] categorised the most common morphing strategies and provided an overview of research in this area from 2020 to 2025. Their study emphasises the importance of adaptive control frameworks and innovative actuation methods, such as shape memory alloys and thermoplastic elastomers, in achieving effective morphing capabilities. The present work focuses primarily on camber morphing applied to the trailing edge.

There are a few dominant approaches to adapting the camber of a wing: metamaterial structures with variable structural characteristics and compliant mechanisms. Compliant mechanisms are typically used in larger aircraft, such as regional jets with a capacity of up to 100 seats [7], [2]. In contrast, metamaterial-based morphing structures are more commonly applied to UAVs [8]. Some studies explore combinations of twist and camber morphing [3], [9], or even integrate sweep angle variation [10]. All of these metamaterial-based approaches incorporate lattice structures with variable properties across the lattice to achieve optimal structural stiffness and aerodynamic performance. The proposed approach differs from all the designs mentioned above in that the main wingbox remains rigid and is manufactured from carbon-fibre composite. The metamaterial lattice replaces only the hinge, which is typically part of compliant mechanism-based morphing solutions. The last noticeable solution is morphing using an elastic load-bearing upper skin, which connects a wing box with a rear rigid control surface part. This approach can also be seen in recent research on morphing wings [11, 12].

2.2. Metamaterials in Aerospace

Metamaterials represent a promising technology for the aerospace industry due to their ability to achieve mechanical properties unattainable with traditional materials. These properties can be tailored across a structure, enabling spatially variable stiffness. An overview of mechanical metamaterials and their unique characteristics was provided by Zadpoor [13]. A notable subclass of metamaterials is auxetic materials, which are characterised by a negative Poisson's ratio—they expand laterally when stretched and contract laterally when compressed. Such materials are suitable not only for applications requiring tailored mechanical properties but also as effective shock absorbers [14, 15]. Another innovative approach involves functionally graded materials. Nian et al. [16] presented the design and additive manufacturing of novel functionally graded lattice beams, investigating their mechanical performance, deformation behaviour, and energy absorption capabilities. Arredondo-Soto et al. [17] reviewed methods of tailoring stiffness in compliant systems using topology optimisation, emphasising the potential of underexplored compliant joints and mechanisms. Their study includes aerospace applications such as aircraft morphing, particularly focusing on wing structure and skin morphing with cellular materials. A specific application of metamaterials in deformable wings was demonstrated by Wang [18]. In general, two primary objectives for metamaterials in structural design are identified: lightweight structures, which are rigid and strength-efficient, and compliant mechanisms, which enable the transmission of motion and force. A further example of compliant mechanism use is the flexure hinge design described by Liu et al. [19].

2.3. Multidisciplinary approach

This section presents a comprehensive literature review centred on multidisciplinary design optimisation (MDO), emphasising the integration of aerodynamic and structural analyses. The review explores the implementation of these disciplines, aiming to enhance the efficiency and performance of design processes.

2.3.1. Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation

MDO is an approach to designing complex systems that involves optimising across various disciplines. Martins and Lambe [20] provide a comprehensive overview of MDO architectures, covering both monolithic and distributed architectures along with their various combinations. They also introduced the eXtended Design Structure Matrix (XDSM) visualisation standard for MDO architectures [21], which is utilised in this study. In the context of morphing wing applications, the integration of aerodynamic and structural analyses is typical. It gains advantage from MDO approach to get optimal design. One of the pioneering studies in morphing wing MDO was introduced by Rajagopal [22], focusing on the preliminary wing design of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) using a two-step optimisation approach. The first step involves single-objective aerodynamic optimisation, followed by a coupled dual-objective optimisation in the second step, integrating aerodynamics and structural considerations. The use of Kriging models as surrogate models helps in reducing computational costs, while genetic algorithms and Pareto fronts are employed in the second optimisation step. Another notable application is demonstrated by de Gaspari [1], where a four-level multidisciplinary optimisation is applied to the morphing leading edge of a 50-seater regional aircraft. The optimisation process includes aerodynamic optimisation, topology optimisation of the compliant rib, integration of material characteristics, and stress analysis on a half-wing 3D model. The design process culminates in Pareto-optimal solutions that balance conflicting requirements and multiple design load conditions. Further applications of MDO in morphing wing technologies are explored by Dexl et al. [23].

No universally optimal MDO architecture exists for aerospace design applications, as the choice depends on many factors such as the number of disciplines involved, the number of design variables, available computational resources, and the level of model fidelity required [20]. Typically, multi-level optimisation is employed when the goal is a detailed design of an aircraft or its components. In this work, a monolithic Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF) architecture is used. This choice is motivated by the relatively small size of the research team and the adoption of a simplified 2.5-dimensional modelling approach. Specifically, the individual disciplinary analyses (aerodynamic, structural, and control) are conducted in a two-dimensional setting, while the implementation of the objective function introduces variables in the third, spanwise dimension, extending the airfoil section results across the entire wing and UAV.

2.3.2. Integration of aerodynamics

The choice of method used to evaluate the aerodynamic properties of an optimised aircraft component depends on the required level of fidelity. In cases where flow is expected to exhibit nonlinear behavior, such as in transonic regimes, conditions involving significant flow separation, or near-stall situations, high-fidelity numerical methods, such as Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), are commonly employed within multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) frameworks, as demonstrated among others by [24]. In contrast, in subsonic regimes with minimal or no flow separation—such as during cruise or loiter flight conditions—low-fidelity methods can provide sufficiently accurate aerodynamic predictions.

For two-dimensional flow around airfoils, a widely used low-fidelity tool is XFOIL [25], which has been employed in various aerostructural optimisation studies. For example, [26] used XFOIL for the aerostructural optimisation of a morphing wing demonstrator, while [23] applied it in the multidisciplinary optimisation of an active morphing wing section.

Another option is the MSES code [27], which is a two-dimensional compressible viscous/inviscid interaction code that solves the Euler equations coupled with the boundary layer equations. It is particularly well-suited for analysing multi-element airfoils in subsonic and transonic flow regimes. This tool was used by [28] for the aerodynamic optimisation of a multi-element airfoil.

2.3.3. Analysis of lattice structures

Typically, numerical methods such as the finite element method are employed to predict the physical behaviour of lattice structures. However, due to their intricate geometry, the computations involved are computationally expensive. In order to optimise such structures with a reasonable computational effort, special methods have been developed. One

commonly used method is the homogenization method [29, 30], where the detailed geometry is replaced by a bulk material with properties obtained by the analysis of a single cell. However, two requirements are necessary: a large enough separation of scale and periodicity. Both are not fulfilled when analysing functionally graded lattice structures with a low number of unit cells.

Another approach is to employ reduced order models [31, 32], which require custom finite element solvers. A less intrusive method is to rely on mechanical truss [33] or beam [34, 35] modelling. The advantage of this method is that many existing finite element software packages can be used. However, the applicability of beam models is limited to lattice structures composed of slender struts or extruded thin shells, where effects in extrusion direction can be neglected.

3. Methods

The wing shape and size are inspired by the Smart-X wing [36]. It features a rectangular planform with a span of 3.8 m and a chord length of 600 mm. The selected undeformed airfoil is the NACA 2510. The optimisation process is simplified to a two-dimensional task represented by a single rib. A wing section comprising two adjacent ribs is designed to manufacture a demonstrator. Only the control component operates on the full-span wing, assuming that the morphing trailing edge extends along the entire span except for the central part located within the fuselage. The metamaterial lattice is positioned behind the wing box, which is placed at 55% of the wing chord from the leading edge. The following subsections describe the wing section with a metamaterial lattice, introduce the metamaterial lattice design, and outline the disciplines involved in the multidisciplinary design approach.

3.1. Wing section with metamaterial-based trailing edge hinge

The model of the morphing wing section is shown in Figure 1. It consists of a wing box, a rigid leading edge, and a morphing trailing edge.

Figure 1: Morphing wing section

The wing box and leading edge are designed to be manufactured from carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP). The wing box acts as the main structural component of the wing section, providing support for the morphing trailing edge. In a real aircraft, the wing box carries the primary structural loads, including aerodynamic and inertial forces, and transfers them to the fuselage through the root rib. It also transmits actuation forces from control and high-lift surfaces. In this demonstrator, the wing box segment fulfils the same role. The structure must maintain its structural integrity and avoid instabilities such as buckling during testing and evaluation of the morphing capability. A detailed illustration of the morphing trailing edge concept is shown in Figure 2.

Morphing of the trailing edge is achieved via a compliant hinge based on a metamaterial lattice composed of unit cells with an X-shaped cross-section. The remainder of the trailing edge rib is rigid, and both upper and lower skins are made of CFRP. The upper skin is continuously connected to the wing box, while the lower skin is split into two segments to allow for a change in length during morphing.

MDO of Metamaterial-Based Morphing Wing

Figure 2: Components of the morphing trailing edge

3.1.1. Metamaterial lattice design

The local stiffness of the lattice varies gradually and is controlled by tuning the unit cell angle, shown in Fig. 3 (a), where the unit cell angle varies from the stiffest value of 0° to the most flexible value of 90° . Our approach follows the idea of [37], where a parametrised unit cell is composed into a lattice structure using spline composition. The main idea is to fill a given macroscopic structure, in our case, the cross-section of a wing, with a parametrised unit cell. The shape of the individual unit cells is then determined by a spline-based parametrisation function. This approach allows the design of complex lattice structures with a comparatively low number of design parameters, which are the control points of the spline used to define the parametrisation function. Additionally, the overall stiffness of the lattice can be adjusted by the cross-section of the individual struts.

Figure 3: Trailing edge lattice structure geometry parametrisation.

Material Selection, Lattice Topology Integration with Wing Section: Boundary/interface conditions and modelling assumptions.

3.2. Disciplines Involved

This section specifies the disciplines involved in MDO. Aerodynamic, structural, and control analyses are described, and their implementations are introduced.

3.2.1. Aerodynamic analysis

The aerodynamic properties of primary interest in this study are the lift coefficient (C_L), drag coefficient (C_D), pitching moment coefficient (C_M), and surface pressure coefficient (C_p) of the morphed wing airfoil. These quantities are evaluated for the wing airfoil using MSES, a two-dimensional, compressible viscous/inviscid interaction code that solves the Euler equations coupled with boundary layer equations. An interface to MSES is provided by the AeroSandbox (ASB) toolbox [38], implemented in Python. ASB integrates a variety of low-fidelity methods for wing and aircraft analysis and offers a framework for gradient-based aerodynamic shape optimisation via algorithmic differentiation. In this work, the ASB–MSES interface was extended to extract the surface pressure coefficient distribution (C_p), which is essential for structural coupling in aeroelastic analyses, as an additional output from the MSES solver.

All MSES grid parameters were set to their default values, except for those listed in Table 1. The solver was configured to compute the flow field for the Mach and Reynolds numbers corresponding to specific flight conditions (loiter and cruise). Natural transition to a turbulent boundary layer was assumed.

Table 1
Mesh parameters for airfoil simulation.

Parameter	Value
Airfoil side points	261
Inlet points on leftmost airfoil streamline	41
Outlet points on rightmost airfoil streamline	41

The configuration parameters relevant to this application and used in the MSES analysis are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2
Mesh parameters for airfoil simulation.

Parameter	Description	Value
ISMOM	Set use S-momentum equation, with isentropic condition only near leading edge	3
IFFBC	Set to use vortex+source+doublet airfoil far-field BCs	2
ACRIT	Amplification factor n_{crit}	9.0
MUCON	Artificial dissipation coefficient	-1

3.2.2. Structural analysis

The mechanical behaviour of the lattice structure is determined by means of the Finite Element Method (FEM). Because the proposed lattice structure consists of thin extrusions, shell modelling could be employed. However, since the deformation does not change in the extrusion direction, the behaviour can be further simplified and described by beam models. The commercial software Abaqus is used, and first-order, shear-deformable beam elements (B21) are used. Python scripts are written to automatically generate the geometry and Abaqus input files. In particular, the open source spline toolbox *Splinepy* [39] is used for the spline-based geometry generation. The input of the mechanical static simulation is the pressure distribution determined by the aerodynamic analysis, as well as the actuator force. As a simplification, both the attachment to the wingbox and the attachment to the rest of the trailing edge wing are assumed to be rigid. Due to this simplification, instead of using the pressure as the load, a resultant force and moment can be calculated and applied at an arbitrary point on the right-hand side of the lattice structure. All degrees of freedom are locked on the left-hand side of the lattice structure to mimic the connection to the wingbox. The boundary conditions are schematically shown in Figure 4 with the resultant forces and moments acting on the right-hand side. The material properties of the lattice were assumed to be linear with a constant elastic modulus of 1050 MPa and a Poisson ratio of 0.3. The elastic modulus of the skin is estimated to be 98857 MPa. A linear elastic analysis under consideration of nonlinear geometric changes is performed to determine the deformed geometry under aerodynamic loading. The analysis does not consider the material's static and fatigue failure criteria.

3.2.3. Control analysis

Since a conventional tail unit UAV with a rudder and elevator is assumed in this work, only the ailerons are designed as morphing controls and control requirements are defined only for rolling motion. The roll rate requirement is specified in CS-VLA certification specifications [40], paragraph 157, for take-off and approach flight phases. This requirement demands the ability to reverse a 30-degree banked turn to the opposite direction within a specified time. Additionally, recommendations are provided for maximum non-dimensional roll rates, which should not be less than 0.09 for high manoeuvrability aircraft [41]. These values are used as criteria for the roll rate requirement. Assuming an aileron size extending from the wingtip to the mid-span and a chordwise depth of 45 per cent from the trailing edge, a preliminary unsteady roll analysis done according to the method by Phillips [41] indicates a minimum required asymmetric trailing edge deflection of 7°.

The implementation of the control component in the MDO process is driven by the requirement that the trailing-edge actuator must generate sufficient moment to achieve the desired roll rates. To ensure robustness, we selected the

Figure 4: Trailing Edge Boundary Conditions

most demanding scenario for the actuator: cruise speed combined with maximum downward trailing-edge deflection, where aerodynamic and structural loads act together against the actuator force. Within the MDO framework, the control component identifies the lightest servo capable of meeting the required actuating force specification. For each servo, the actuating force is derived from a kinematic transmission ratio, ensuring sufficient rod displacement and speed. The kinematic transmission ratio is a ratio between the angular displacement of the servo and the linear displacement of the rod acting force on the metamaterial lattice. Servo's rated torque is calculated as half of stall torque, and the actuator force is then obtained from the rated torque and the kinematic transmission ratio. The selection is made from a database of 30 commercially available servos of varying sizes and power ratings. The output of the control component is the mass of the selected servo. The servo mass is increased by 50 per cent, which is estimated for a kinematic mechanism and servo mounting to the wing. The estimation is based on our experience with a demonstrator of a morphing wing section design.

3.3. Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation

The proposed architecture of the MDO framework, together with a detailed description of the optimisation problem and its settings, is outlined below.

3.3.1. Proposed MDO architecture

An overview of the proposed MDO architecture and its structure is provided in this paragraph. The detailed algorithm is illustrated using the XDMS diagram shown in Fig. 5. A Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF) architecture has been adopted, as the aerodynamic and structural analyses are tightly coupled. The loop, governed by a 2D MDA component, is executed three times—once for each of the three flight regimes: cruise, loiter, and manoeuvre. A control component then selects the appropriate actuator, followed by a final component that evaluates the constraints and objective function. The proposed architecture is monolithic, featuring a single optimiser that manages the design vector and minimises the objective function.

3.3.2. Optimisation problem formulation

The design vector, constraints and objectives are introduced in this section. The design vector includes variables related to the metamaterial lattice design and its distribution along the span. Specifically, it contains six unit cell angle values that define the lattice geometry (see Fig. 3). The overall lattice geometry is defined using a spline. Other design variables include the lattice thickness and the distance between adjacent ribs, which determine the final number of ribs along the span. The leading edge and box wing design is excluded from both the design vector and the MDO process.

Only a few constraints are defined within the MDO algorithm. Lift coefficient constraints are prescribed with a tolerance of 0.05 around target values of 0.219 in cruise and 0.609 in loiter regimes. Then, limits on TE deflections are prescribed in all flight regimes. In the manoeuvre regime, a minimum TE deflection of 7° is required, while in

Figure 5: MDO architecture visualised using XDSM method. The Aerodynamic-Structural loop is repeated three times for the following flight regimes: cruise, loiter, and manoeuvre.

loiter and cruise, the TE deflection is limited to a maximum of 10° . Since the genetic algorithm has been used, the constraints were applied in the form of a penalty term added to the objective function.

The objective function represents the negative value of the normalised range and endurance. Two steps are taken to extend the results of the 2D analyses to the overall UAV performance. First, the induced drag coefficient is calculated from the lift coefficient and added to the airfoil drag coefficient. An Oswald efficiency factor of 0.84 was estimated using the method described by [42].

$$c_{Di} = \frac{c_L^2}{\pi A Re} \quad (1)$$

$$c_{D,cruise} = c_{Daf1,cruise} + c_{Di,cruise} \quad (2)$$

$$c_{D,loiter} = c_{Daf1,loiter} + c_{Di,loiter} \quad (3)$$

The second step is the calculation of battery mass for the main propulsion of the UAV. The objective function operates with a take-off mass of 50 kg, as defined by the research project. A potentially high number of actuators and their associated mass negatively impact the available battery mass for the propulsion, assuming a constant payload. The battery mass is calculated as the default battery mass of 6 kg minus the total actuator mass. The actuator mass is determined based on the number of ribs, which is derived from the rib spacing, a variable in the design vector.

$$m_{batt} = m_{batt,0} - m_{act} n_{rib} \quad (4)$$

The range and endurance equations within the objective function are normalised. The normalization factor for range is 5.2×10^5 m, and for endurance, it is 2.08×10^4 s. These weighting factors ensure that both parameters are equally

Table 3
Optimisation problem setup

Objective	$\min f_{\text{Objective}}(d)$
Constraints	
Lift coefficient (cruise)	$c_{L,\text{cruise,min}} \leq c_{L,\text{cruise}} \leq c_{L,\text{cruise,max}}$
Lift coefficient (loiter)	$c_{L,\text{loiter,min}} \leq c_{L,\text{loiter}} \leq c_{L,\text{loiter,max}}$
TE deflection (loiter)	$TE_{\text{rot,loiter,min}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,loiter}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,loiter,max}}$
TE deflection (cruise)	$TE_{\text{rot,cruise,min}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,cruise}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,cruise,max}}$
TE deflection (manoeuvre)	$TE_{\text{rot,manoeuvre,min}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,manoeuvre}} \leq TE_{\text{rot,manoeuvre,max}}$
Actuator force (cruise)	$F_{\text{act,cruise,min}} \leq F_{\text{act,cruise}} \leq F_{\text{act,cruise,max}}$
Actuator force (loiter)	$F_{\text{act,loiter,min}} \leq F_{\text{act,loiter}} \leq F_{\text{act,loiter,max}}$
Actuator force (manoeuvre)	$F_{\text{act,manoeuvre,min}} \leq F_{\text{act,manoeuvre}} \leq F_{\text{act,manoeuvre,max}}$
Angle of attack (cruise)	$\alpha_{\text{cruise,min}} \leq \alpha_{\text{cruise}} \leq \alpha_{\text{cruise,max}}$
Angle of attack (loiter)	$\alpha_{\text{loiter,min}} \leq \alpha_{\text{loiter}} \leq \alpha_{\text{loiter,max}}$
Design Variable Bounds	
Lattice thickness	$d_{\text{Latt,min}} \leq d_{\text{Latt}} \leq d_{\text{Latt,max}}$
Lattice unit cell angle	$\phi_{\text{min}} \leq \phi \leq \phi_{\text{max}}$
Rib distance	$d_{\text{rib,min}} \leq d_{\text{rib}} \leq d_{\text{rib,max}}$

important and that the objective function is expressed in a non-dimensional form. The objective is defined as negative because the optimiser searches for a minimum.

The other constants used in the equations are: $\eta_{\text{total}} = 0.73$, representing the total efficiency factor (covering both propeller and engine efficiency); $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$, the gravitational acceleration; $\rho_0 = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the air density at sea level; and $S_w = 2.28 \text{ m}^2$, the wing surface area.

$$R_{\text{cruise}} = \frac{E_{\text{batt}}}{g} \cdot \frac{c_{L,\text{cruise}}}{c_{D,\text{cruise}}} \cdot \frac{m_{\text{batt}}}{m_{\text{tow}}} \cdot \eta_{\text{total}} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{\text{loiter}} = \frac{E_{\text{batt}}}{g^{3/2}} \cdot \frac{c_{L,\text{loiter}}^{3/2}}{c_{D,\text{loiter}}} \cdot \frac{m_{\text{batt}}}{m_{\text{tow}}^{3/2}} \cdot \frac{\rho_0 S_w}{2} \cdot \eta_{\text{total}} \quad (6)$$

$$f_{\text{Objective}} = - \left(\frac{R_{\text{cruise}}}{R_{\text{norm}}} + \frac{E_{\text{loiter}}}{E_{\text{norm}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

3.3.3. Optimiser Setup

The optimisation problem can be summarised as follows in Table 3. The vector of design variables is defined as:

$$d = \{d_{\text{Latt}}, \phi, \alpha_{\text{cruise}}, \alpha_{\text{loiter}}, F_{\text{act,cruise}}, F_{\text{act,loiter}}, F_{\text{act,manoeuvre}}, d_{\text{rib}}\}.$$

This optimisation problem could be solved using a variety of optimisation algorithms. However, we opt for a genetic algorithm due to the following reasons. First, derivatives of the objective function with respect to the design variables are not necessary. Second, it is less likely to be stuck in local minima, and third, it is robust against non-converging simulations and outliers. The latter is especially relevant in our case, as both the aerodynamic as well as the solid mechanics simulations do not converge for all geometries and loadings. We use the simple genetic algorithm available in the OpenMDAO software package [43]. It uses crossover and mutation to update the design vector at each generation. After each generation, tournament selection is employed to choose which design vector is kept for the next generation. Additionally, the worst-performing design vector is replaced by the best. The objective function is extended by the penalty terms defined by parameter p and the exponent κ , which together form the fitness function:

$$f_{\text{Fitness}}(d) = f_{\text{Objective}}(d) + p \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{N_g} (\delta_k \cdot g_k(d)^\kappa) + p \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} |h_k(d)|^\kappa \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\delta_k = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } g_k(d) \leq 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } g_k(d) > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

and g_k denotes the N_g inequality constraints and h_k the N_h equality constraints. We choose p to be 50 and κ to be 1. In addition to the inequality constraints above, we add an equality constraint that penalises simulations that did not converge.

4. Results

This section presents the optimal design of the morphing metamaterial lattice and other parameters, including convergence characteristics. The genetic algorithm converged after 3,162 cases within 49 generations. The time progression of the objective function is shown in Figure 6. The boxplot illustrates the median and interquartile range, which contains the middle 50% of the data. The whiskers indicate variability outside the upper and lower quartiles, extending up to 1.5 times the interquartile range. Any data points beyond the whiskers are considered outliers and are plotted individually. Most outliers are connected to divergence in aerodynamic and structural analyses loop within the MDO. The minimum value of the objective function reached -0.994648.

Figure 6: Boxplot showing convergence along generations

The aerodynamic characteristics at the optimum are shown in Table 4. In the manoeuvre case, the lift coefficient was not evaluated, and the angle of attack was assumed to be the same as in the cruise regime. The control component selected the servo FS5115M-FB [44] from the company Pololu for the optimal solution. The servo weight is 72 g. The optimum distance between ribs converged to 378 mm, resulting in 11 ribs along the wingspan. The lattice geometry converged to the shape shown in Figure 7, with a final lattice thickness of 29 mm. The most flexible cells are located along the diagonal from the upper left to the lower right corners of the lattice, while the most rigid cells are placed on the upper right corner, except for the corner cell, which contains only one control point with a positive unit cell angle.

5. Discussion

This section discusses the results and highlights some limitations of the study. Figure 6 presents statistics for all optimisation results, including both valid solutions and those that either failed to meet constraints or did not converge.

Figure 7: Optimised lattice geometry

Table 4
Aerodynamic characteristics at the optimum solution

Flight Condition	Lift Coefficient (C_L)	Angle of Attack ($^\circ$)	TE Deflection ($^\circ$)
Cruise	0.2936	0.5963	-0.3791
Loiter	0.6240	3.767	-0.4953
Manoeuvre	–	0.5963	7.847

The number of valid results increased from one in the first two generations to 19 in the 43rd and 47th generations. The optimal solution belongs to the 47th generation out of a total of 49. The 48th generation contains a solution with an objective function value nearly equal to that of the optimum. Both solutions feature similar lattice geometries, and the control component selected the same servo.

The optimal solution converged near the constraint of 7° deflection of TE for the manoeuvre case. This deflection value does not represent the maximum possible deflection, but rather the deflection required to generate a sufficient roll moment. Compared to standard ailerons, this value is relatively low due to the large size of the TE morphing surface. The TE surface is larger than conventional ailerons, both spanwise and chordwise. The required deflection is achieved with a control force of 79.5 N, while the servo is capable of delivering 113 N with the used transmission ratio.

The optimal solution from the MDO process was used to design a demonstrator of the wing section using the metamaterial lattice hinge. The kinematic mechanism of the selected servo was modelled and 3D printed using PLA. The entire mechanism, including steel shafts and servo mounting screws, weighs 20 g. Assuming 50% of the servo weight is used by the mechanism, approximately 35 g remains available for servo cables within the wing. The mechanism has a transmission ratio of 4.666 mm/rad. This ratio was chosen to provide sufficient deflection speed ($20^\circ/s$) while maximising actuator torque.

A comparison between the morphing wing with a metamaterial lattice hinge and a conventional wing with ailerons reveals several benefits. The primary advantage of the lattice-based design is its simplicity. It can be manufactured using a 3D printer and assembled without the need for rotating hinge axes. This results in a clean aerodynamic surface with no gaps. However, a potential drawback might be fatigue. Fatigue life was not evaluated in this study, though preliminary low-cycle tests of the nylon lattice showed promising results with low deflections up to 10° . Based on these results, it can be stated that the metamaterial lattice hinge can replace the standard hinge axis at the aileron.

Let us discuss the trade-offs between aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and control authority in the proposed design. The objective function includes all these aspects and leads to a lattice with variable stiffness. The optimal shape provided the best range and endurance performance given by lift and drag coefficients and the required weight of all servos and their mechanisms. The lattice is more flexible in deflection downward, where the aerodynamic

loading and structural strain act together against the control force. And the lattice is more resistant in the upward direction when aerodynamic loading acts against structural strain from deformation, thereby decreasing the required control force.

An important aspect of control and structural design is the size of the movable TE. Typical ailerons require maximum deflections of around 25° . However, when the full span is used as an aileron, an unsymmetrical deflection of only 4.2° is sufficient to achieve a nondimensional roll rate of 0.09. If only half the span is used, a deflection of 6.2° is needed to reach the same roll rate.

The NACA 2510 airfoil has been used as the reference starting point for all aerodynamic and structural analyses. Structural loading results from the combined effects of deformation and aerodynamic forces. Introducing an additional design parameter to define the trailing edge deflection under zero structural load could reduce the required control force. This zero-load deflection could be achieved by manufacturing the structure with a predefined deformed shape.

One of the main limitations of the proposed solution is the two-dimensional setup of the aerodynamic and structural analyses. The best performance would likely be achieved with a trailing edge capable of morphing with a continuously varying deflection along the span. This could be accomplished by dividing the trailing edge into multiple segments, as demonstrated in the Smart-X wing [36]. More segments would enable an approximation of continuous spanwise morphing. Another approach would be to extend the current design into three dimensions, utilising more powerful 3D computational tools. This method was applied by Wang et al. [45], resulting in multidimensional morphing, where the forebody of a streamlined structure can adapt its shape in any direction. However, in such cases, maintaining sufficient stiffness in the flexible skin becomes a major challenge.

Further work on the morphing wing project is focused on the manufacturing of a physical demonstrator. The demonstrator has been designed based on the MDO results and is currently in the manufacturing phase. The next steps will include wind tunnel testing and a fatigue test of the metamaterial nylon lattice. A future development goal is to extend the design to a fully three-dimensional wing, aiming to exploit the benefits of morphing across various flight regimes, such as combinations of high lift configuration with roll moment when the TE will work as a flap and aileron together.

6. Conclusions

This study explored the feasibility and performance of a morphing wing section using a metamaterial-based trailing edge through a multidisciplinary design optimisation (MDO) framework. Two main research questions were addressed: whether a metamaterial lattice can effectively replace a conventional trailing-edge hinge, and what trade-offs arise between aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and control authority.

The results demonstrate that the proposed metamaterial lattice enables sufficient trailing edge (TE) deflection, which exceeds the required 7° in the manoeuvre flight regime, while maintaining structural integrity and remaining within the capabilities of lightweight commercial servos. The optimised design achieved this through a variable-stiffness nylon metamaterial lattice and minimal actuator mass, enabling adequate roll control without the need for traditional hinged mechanisms.

The MDO process converged to an optimal design of a two-dimensional airfoil, extended to a three-dimensional case by estimating induced drag in the objective function and determining the optimal number and size of servos to achieve the best performance. The clean surface integration and simplified actuation mechanism represent a promising path forward for UAV morphing applications.

Future work will focus on the manufacturing and experimental testing of a physical demonstrator based on the optimised design. This includes wind tunnel validation, fatigue testing of the nylon lattice, and potential extension to a full three-dimensional morphing wing configuration. These steps will further assess the feasibility of metamaterial-based morphing control surfaces in aerospace systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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References

- [1] A. De Gaspari, Multiobjective optimization for the aero-structural design of adaptive compliant wing devices, *Applied Sciences* 10 (2020) 6380, DOI: 10.3390/app10186380.
- [2] M. C. Noviello, B. Galasso, I. Dimino, S. Ameduri, A. Concilio, Trade-off conceptual design of a camber morphing flap for the next generation hybrid electrical aircraft across the herwingt project, *Applied Sciences* 15 (2025) 3660, DOI: 10.3390/app15073660.
- [3] X. Zhu, J. Zhang, W. Chen, H. Gu, Tension-twist coupling morphing wing using a novel mechanical metamaterial, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 155 (2024) 109745, DOI: 10.1016/j.ast.2024.109745.
- [4] A. E. Rivero, P. M. Weaver, J. E. Cooper, B. K. Woods, Parametric structural modelling of fish bone active camber morphing aerofoils, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures* 29 (2018) 2008–2026, DOI: 10.1177/1045389X18758182.
- [5] Anonymised, <https://anonymised/>, 2023. [Accessed 24-07-2025].
- [6] M. N. Mowla, D. Asadi, T. Durhasan, J. R. Jafari, M. Amoozgar, Recent advancements in morphing applications: Architecture, artificial intelligence integration, challenges, and future trends-a comprehensive survey, *Aerospace Science and Technology* (2025) 110102, DOI: 10.1016/j.ast.2025.110102.
- [7] S. Ameduri, B. Galasso, M. C. Noviello, I. Dimino, A. Concilio, P. Catalano, F. A. D'Aniello, G. M. Carossa, L. Pinazo, J. Derry, et al., Design and optimization of a compliant morphing trailing edge for high-lift generation, *Applied Sciences* 15 (2025) 2529, DOI: 10.3390/app15052529.
- [8] Z. Wang, Q. Wu, Y. Lu, P. Bao, Y. Yang, D. Li, X. Sun, J. Xiang, Design of a distributedly active morphing wing based on digital metamaterials, *Aerospace* 9 (2022) 762, DOI: 10.3390/aerospace9120762.
- [9] D. Morton, A. Xu, A. Matute, R. F. Shepherd, Autonomous material composite morphing wing, *Journal of Composite Materials* 57 (2023) 711–720, DOI: 10.1177/00219983231151397.
- [10] H. Yang, S. Jiang, Y. Wang, H. Xiao, Design, kinematic and fluid-structure interaction analysis of a morphing wing, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 143 (2023) 108721, DOI: 10.1016/j.ast.2023.108721.
- [11] G. Cheng, T. Ma, J. Yang, N. Chang, X. Zhou, Design and experiment of a seamless morphing trailing edge, *Aerospace* 10 (2023) 282, DOI: 10.3390/aerospace10030282.
- [12] L. Dubnický, J. Juracka, J. Šplíchal, F. Löffelmann, J. Bartoněk, Preliminary design of morphing flaperon using optimization by genetic algorithm, *Aircraft Engineering and Aerospace Technology* (2025), DOI: 10.1108/AEAT-11-2024-0329.
- [13] A. A. Zadpoor, Mechanical meta-materials, *Materials Horizons* 3 (2016) 371–381, DOI: 10.1039/C6MH00065G.
- [14] H. M. A. Kolken, A. A. Zadpoor, Auxetic mechanical metamaterials, *RSC Advances* 7 (2017) 5111–5129, DOI: 10.1039/C6RA27333E.
- [15] X. Ren, R. Das, P. Tran, T. D. Ngo, Y. M. Xie, Auxetic metamaterials and structures: A review, *Smart materials and structures* 27 (2018) 023001, DOI: 10.1088/1361-665X/aaa61c.
- [16] Y. Nian, S. Wan, M. Avcar, R. Yue, M. Li, 3D printing functionally graded metamaterial structure: Design, fabrication, reinforcement, optimization, *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences* 258 (2023) 108580, DOI: 10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2023.108580.
- [17] M. Arredondo-Soto, E. Cuan-Urquiza, A. Gómez-Espinosa, A Review on Tailoring Stiffness in Compliant Systems, via Removing Material: Cellular Materials and Topology Optimization, *Applied Sciences* 11 (2021) 3538, DOI: 10.3390/app11083538.
- [18] H. V. Wang, A Unit Cell Approach for Lightweight Structure and Compliant Mechanism, Ph.D. thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology, 2005. [arXiv:1853/7561](https://arxiv.org/abs/1853/7561).
- [19] M. Liu, X. Zhang, S. Fatikow, Design and analysis of a multi-notched flexure hinge for compliant mechanisms, *Precision Engineering* 48 (2017) 292–304, DOI: 10.1016/j.precisioneng.2016.12.012.
- [20] J. R. Martins, A. B. Lambe, Multidisciplinary design optimization: a survey of architectures, *AIAA journal* 51 (2013) 2049–2075, DOI: 10.2514/1.J051895.
- [21] A. B. Lambe, J. R. Martins, Extensions to the design structure matrix for the description of multidisciplinary design, analysis, and optimization processes, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 46 (2012) 273–284, DOI: 10.1007/s00158-012-0763-y.
- [22] R. Ganguli, S. Rajagopal, Multidisciplinary design optimization of an uav wing using kriging based multi-objective genetic algorithm, in: 50th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference 17th AIAA/ASME/AHS Adaptive Structures Conference 11th AIAA No, 2009, p. 2219. doi:10.2514/6.2009-2219.
- [23] F. Dextl, A. Hauffe, K. Wolf, Multidisciplinary multi-objective design optimization of an active morphing wing section, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 62 (2020) 2423–2440, DOI: 10.1007/s00158-020-02613-4.
- [24] E. J. Adler, J. R. Martins, Efficient aerostructural wing optimization considering mission analysis, *Journal of Aircraft* 60 (2023) 800–816, DOI: 10.2514/1.C037096.
- [25] M. Drela, Xfoil: An analysis and design system for low reynolds number airfoils, in: *Low Reynolds Number Aerodynamics: Proceedings of the Conference Notre Dame, Indiana, USA, 5–7 June 1989*, Springer, 1989, pp. 1–12.
- [26] T. Mkhoyan, N. R. Thakrar, R. De Breuker, J. Sodja, Morphing wing design using integrated and distributed trailing edge morphing, *Smart Materials and Structures* 31 (2022) 125025, DOI: 10.1088/1361-665X/aca18b.
- [27] M. Drela, A user's guide to mses 3.05, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), Cambridge (2007).
- [28] A. Porta Ko, S. Smid, R. Schmehl, M. Mandru, Optimisation of a multi-element airfoil for a fixed-wing airborne wind energy system, *Energies* 16 (2023) 3521, DOI: 10.3390/en16083521.

- [29] B. Hassani, E. Hinton, A review of homogenization and topology optimization I—homogenization theory for media with periodic structure, *Computers & Structures* 69 (1998) 707–717, DOI: 10.1016/S0045-7949(98)00131-X.
- [30] Y. Wang, L. Zhang, S. Daynes, H. Zhang, S. Feih, M. Y. Wang, Design of graded lattice structure with optimized mesostructures for additive manufacturing, *Materials & Design* 142 (2018) 114–123, DOI: 10.1016/j.matdes.2018.01.011.
- [31] S. McBane, Y. Choi, Component-wise reduced order model lattice-type structure design, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 381 (2021) 113813, DOI: 10.1016/j.cma.2021.113813.
- [32] T. Hirschler, R. Bouclier, P. Antolin, A. Buffa, Reduced Order Modeling based Inexact FETI-DP solver for lattice structures, 2023. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2308.11371. arXiv:2308.11371.
- [33] N. T. Kaminakis, G. E. Stavroulakis, Topology optimization for compliant mechanisms, using evolutionary-hybrid algorithms and application to the design of auxetic materials, *Composites Part B: Engineering* 43 (2012) 2655–2668, DOI: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.03.018.
- [34] M. Xu, Z. Qiu, Free vibration analysis and optimization of composite lattice truss core sandwich beams with interval parameters, *Composite Structures* 106 (2013) 85–95, DOI: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.05.048.
- [35] Y. Tang, A. Kurtz, Y. F. Zhao, Bidirectional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) based design method for lattice structure to be fabricated by additive manufacturing, *Computer-Aided Design* 69 (2015) 91–101, DOI: 10.1016/j.cad.2015.06.001.
- [36] R. De Breuker, T. Mkhoyan, N. Nazeer, V. Stuber, X. Wang, I. Mkhoyan, R. Groves, S. van der Zwaag, J. Sodja, Overview of the smartx wing technology integrator, in: *Actuators*, volume 11, MDPI, 2022, p. 302. doi:10.3390/act11100302.
- [37] J. Zwar, G. Elber, S. Elgeti, Shape Optimization for Temperature Regulation in Extrusion Dies Using Microstructures, *Journal of Mechanical Design* 145 (2022), DOI: 10.1115/1.4056075.
- [38] P. D. Sharpe, R. J. Hansman, *Aerosandbox: A differentiable framework for aircraft design optimization*, Ph.D. thesis, 2021.
- [39] J. Zwar, J. Lee, Splinepy, 2025. URL: <https://github.com/tataratat/splinepy>.
- [40] EASA, Certification Specifications for Very Light Aircraft (CS-VLA), Technical Report CS-VLA, European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), 2019. URL: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/document-library/certification-specifications/cs-vla-amendment-1>, amendment 1, 5 March 2009.
- [41] W. F. Phillips, *Mechanics of Flight*, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, 2010.
- [42] E. Obert, *Aerodynamic design of transport aircraft*, IOS press, 2009.
- [43] J. S. Gray, J. T. Hwang, J. R. R. A. Martins, K. T. Moore, B. A. Naylor, OpenMDAO: An open-source framework for multidisciplinary design, analysis, and optimization, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 59 (2019) 1075–1104, DOI: 10.1007/s00158-019-02211-z.
- [44] Pololu - FEETECH High-Torque Servo FS5115M-FB with Position Feedback — pololu.com, <https://www.pololu.com/product/3443>, 2025. [Accessed 21-07-2025].
- [45] Y. Wang, J. Tao, D. Wu, H. Xiao, H. Guo, S. Gong, X. Li, R. Liu, Design and analysis of morphing forebody mechanisms with smooth shape control points for aerospace vehicles, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 165 (2025) 110488, DOI: 10.1016/j.ast.2025.110488.

Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation of a Morphing Wing Section with a Metamaterial-Based Trailing Edge

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multidisciplinary design optimisation (MDO) of a morphing wing section using a metamaterial-based trailing edge. The study investigates whether a metamaterial lattice structure can effectively replace a conventional hinged control surface and evaluates the trade-offs between aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and control authority. A monolithic MDO framework integrates aerodynamic, structural, and control analyses in a coupled loop, using a genetic algorithm to optimise the lattice geometry and actuators configuration. The objective function maximises range and endurance of a fixed-wing UAV, considering both flight performance in cruise and loiter and actuators' mass penalty. The results show that the proposed design achieves the required trailing-edge deflections with minimal control force and reduced mechanical complexity. Limitations due to modelling simplifications are discussed, and directions for future work are outlined.

Nomenclature

AR	Wing aspect ratio
c_D	Drag coefficient
$c_{D_{afl}}$	Airfoil drag coefficient
C_{D_i}	Induced drag coefficient
c_L	Lift coefficient
c_M	Pitch moment coefficient
c_p	Pressure coefficient
\mathbf{d}	Vector of design variables
d_{Latt}	Metamaterial lattice thickness
d_{rib}	Rib spacing
e	Oswald's efficiency factor
E_{batt}	Battery energy
E_{loiter}	Endurance during the loiter
E_{norm}	Normalized endurance
F	Actuation force

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